

ISic1543

I.Sicily inscription 1543

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---] τ,ξ,λ[ευτᾶ---]
2. μ(ηνῶν) θ ἡ(μερῶν) κ [---]
3. Βιτάλα ο[---]
4. υἱῶ ἐπο[ίησε]
5. ξ,υ,σ[---]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493896

EDR 136084

EDCS 41300014

PHI 175592

PHI 330043

PHI 336055

Bibliography

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